

Creating the Correctional Environment for Personality Development of Children with Autistic Disorders

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Abstract: *A sign of the humanization of the modern pedagogical process is a profound change in its organization, primarily in creating conditions for the formation of a holistic personality of the child. The method of forming speech activity of children with autistic disorders of senior preschool age can act as an organizational and pedagogical system, which includes the functioning of specific conditions: organizational and pedagogical (the main of which - the creation of educational and corrective and communicative environment); general didactic (continuity, stages, system in the content of the formation of speech activity); technological (pedagogical and speech therapy diagnosis - starting and finishing - of the child as a basis for organizing the formation of speech activity of children with autistic disorders of older preschool age). Among the auxiliary conditions can be distinguished cognitive, creative, and communicative. Taking into account the peculiarities of mental, emotional, communicative, and speech development, we anticipate that the level of speech activity in children with autistic disorders will increase under the conditions of implementation of our methodology, and providing selected psychological and pedagogical conditions will accelerate and optimize this process.*

Keywords: *observation of the child, corrective influence, organized environment, emotional state, use of self-stimulation, oversaturation of impressions, stimulation of speech activity.*

How to cite: Bazyma, N., Mamicheva, O., Korhun, L., Krykunenko, Y., Rozina, I., & Dehtiarenko, T. (2022). Creating the Correctional Environment for Personality Development of Children with Autistic Disorders. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 13(1), 259-275. <https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/13.1/283>

Introduction

This article is a follow-up of the previous papers (Bazyma et al., 2020; 2021). The analysis of the general and special psycho-pedagogical literature (Behas et al., 2019; Melnyk et al., 2019; 2021; Sheremet, et al., 2019; Yanushko, 2004), summary of the data obtained during the diagnostic and modeling phase of the experiment and direct observation of children with autistic disorders of older preschool age have made it possible to identify the conditions of a corrective approach to the formation of speech activity in children of this category. They are the following:

- observation of the child and direct interaction with him and an objective assessment of the dynamics of speech activity;
- structuring of corrective influence based on the account of the information received during inspection and supervision of the child;
- creation of an adequately organized environment for corrective action (structuring of mode, time, and space);
- correlation of the child's emotional state to form the motivation to learn new speech material and increase speech activity;
- use of self-stimulation as an integral part of the behavior of a child with autistic disorders to fill it with a new meaning, which will be the basis for the formation of speech activity;
- use of the appropriate number of tasks, the change of which would precede the oversaturation of impressions;
- gradual presentation of tasks with the obligatory use of stimulation as a method of forming motivation for interaction and direct speech activity;
- the relationship in the work of specialists and parents of children with autistic disorders.
- stimulation of speech activity taking into account the peculiarities of communicative-speech activity of a child with autistic disorders (Bazyma et al., 2020; 2021).

Let's try to follow and reveal the selected conditions in more detail.

Observation of the child and direct interaction with him and an objective assessment of the dynamics of speech activity

Considerable attention in the preparation and classes conducting requires analysis of the situation and careful observation of the child's behavior and reactions during independent activities and interaction with people to understand the logic of its actions, focusing on repetitive patterns of behavior, as well as to identify individual behaviors, determining how

comfortable or uncomfortable the child feels in a given situation (for example, outside the child, motor stereotypes and self-stimulations, voice intonation, etc.). The obtained data can provide important material about the mood and condition of the child, even if he is not able to report it himself. Knowing what manifestations of the condition and mood are the appropriate actions of the child, we can focus on them, and we can make the lesson more productive and meaningful.

Also of great importance in the success of correctional work is the correct assessment of the dynamics of the child's development, because often new ways of responding to a situation, new behaviors are difficult to assess unambiguously. To increase the accuracy of assessment of changes in verbal, communicative, and behavioral manifestations of the child, Yanushko (2004) advises establishing a "starting point", namely the initial level of opportunities for its interaction with the environment, and considers the novations in comparison with this point". By noting the changes taking place with the child, it is possible to find out how well the interaction with him was organized and how well the correctional process takes place, as well as to build new guidelines, directions, and tasks of further educational and correctional work.

Thus, we emphasize the importance of constant analysis of the situation in the process of monitoring the child and direct interaction with him, and an objective assessment of the dynamics of speech activity in a child with autistic disorders (Bazyra et al., 2020; 2021).

Structuring the corrective effect based on the information obtained during the examination and observation of the child

Of course, the provision of correctional care is impossible without accurately determining the level of interaction with the environment available to a child with autistic disorders, because its excess can cause her to avoid possible contact, unwanted protest reactions such as negativity, aggression or self-aggression, and, most undesirably, negative communication experiences. After all, according to research by many scientists (Lebedynskiy, & Bardyshevskaya, 2006; Ostrovska, 2013; Yanushko, 2004), children with autism tend to perceive information about the environment in blocks, strongly linking some a situation or event with a feeling or emotion, which in the future, in the event of such a situation, can associatively cause the full range of feelings and emotions experienced by the child when he first encountered it. Therefore, there is no doubt about the need to establish the most adequate level of contact with the world and

people at the moment on the appropriate parameters of the most acceptable distance of communication, research and examination of objects, the duration of focus on interesting subjects, favorite activities when the child is alone, use of toys, ways to calm down when aroused, attitude to the inclusion of adults in the classroom, the presence of stereotypes and their quality, the use of speech, its nature and purpose.

Observations of the child's behavior can provide information about the child's ability to interact spontaneously with the environment and people around him in everyday life, and in specially created situations of interaction. Social relationships are difficult for people with autistic disorders, and even more so for preschoolers since they have little ability to model behavior depending on the situation. Even after developing a certain behavioral set, a child with autistic disorders is not always able to choose between a more effective and less effective way to achieve the goal. Reducing the severity of behavioral stereotypes is possible only with help, and this is due to certain emotional experiences. It is difficult for a child with autistic disorders to be in a state of change that can cause effective fluctuations. Constantly changing environment can be traumatic, but at the same time resourceful for increasing one's social effectiveness. The data revealed during the observation allow concluding the possibilities of interaction of a child with autistic disorders of older preschool age with others and the level of endurance in contact with the environment at present to structure the corrective effect based on information obtained during examination and observation for the child.

Creating an adequately organized environment for corrective action

It is known that children with autistic disorders are characterized by a desire for consistency and permanence of the daily routine, in clothing, food, etc. Therefore, it is very important to be supported the sequence and regularity of regime moments of each day, and it is recommended to prepare the child in advance for the necessary innovations and changes.

It is known that people with autism have an underdeveloped sense of time (Zyumalla, 2005), so it is difficult for them to track its course, which affects the inability to change some activities during the day, especially given the passion for some actions and intolerance or reluctance to perform others and sometimes reduced sensitivity to hunger, cold, pain. Therefore, in most cases, it is proposed to develop a daily schedule that repeats the passion of children with autistic disorders to recurrence and stereotyping, reduces the number of unexpected events that can cause anxiety, fear, or stress, and achieve the ability to anticipate, plan, however, due to "looping" and limiting

the possibility of gaining new experience.

The most accessible stereotypical behavior for some children with autistic disorders may be used to some extent for correctional or educational purposes. First, the usual stereotypes for the child help to protect he/she from an emotional breakdown, to start more likely his/her activity inadequate contact with the environment, to consolidate the achievements by repeated (albeit initially stereotypical) repetition. We mean not only the formation of the skill of following the rules and following the regime moments but also regularly talking about what is happening, commenting on all the details, explaining the functional and emotional meaning of each of them, releasing patterns and relationships. Even if a child with autism does not respond actively, this does not mean that he or she does not perceive or assimilate information. But, on the other hand, the excessive tendency to repeat the established order and the predominance of stereotypical reactions to any stimuli can be an obstacle to the development of more natural and flexible ways of interacting with the environment.

Just as it is important to allocate time by appropriate intervals, each of which has its content (sleep, food, study, games, walks, etc.), it is also desirable to mark the space in which the child lives. Such marking can occur due to the constant emotional commenting by adults of what usually happens in this place: food, clothing, games, training, etc. The design of the room should facilitate orientation and give the child unambiguous information about the functions of each zone. The game and work areas must be separated from each other. Knowing what she is asked to do, the child can anticipate and plan their actions in some way (Zyumalla, 2005), and confusion and lack of orientation in the situation can increase the level of anxiety.

Features of rigid and inconvenient adherence of children with autistic constancy of place and time can be used to help the child understand their meaning. Even when the already established rigid stereotype of the child includes seemingly meaningless ritual actions, they should also try to fill them with a general semantic context. In this case, the child makes them less stressed. For example, if a child needs to open and close the door several times when entering the room, you can ask him: "Check if the door closes well."

It is known how children with autistic disorders can be dependent on the surrounding sensory field. On the one hand, this creates enormous difficulties in their arbitrary organization, because random impressions distract them, they may be too immersed in the selective feelings or to avoid interaction if there is a negative stimulus. On the other hand, a well-thought-

out sensory organization of the environment avoids impressions that negatively affect the child's interaction with the environment and fills the environment with stimuli that will motivate the child to certain actions planned by the teacher and giving them the desired sequence. Based on the above, we recommend adhering to the conditions of creating an adequately organized environment for corrective action (structuring mode, time, and space).

Correlation of the child's emotional condition to form the motivation to learn new speech material and increase speech activity

Rapid saturation, even with pleasant impressions, leads to the fact that sometimes children really cannot wait for the promised; need time to experience the received impression or information; independently helpless in a situation of choice. All of the above provokes delayed reactions to certain stimuli and the desire to stereotype the interaction with the outside world.

Children with autistic disorders are very sensitive to the intonation with which they are addressed, the emotional state of loved ones - especially easily transmitted to them anxiety, insecurity - they suffer from discomfort. But due to the immaturity of the emotional sphere, feelings can often be expressed not by empathy, but by the deterioration of their condition, increased fears, aggressive behavior. It is important to teach a child not only to control their emotional manifestations, but also to be able to "read", understand the emotional manifestations of others - first loved ones, and then - everyone with whom you have to communicate. This can be done by commenting on the emotional states of the child, the people she interacts with, cartoon characters, movies, fairy tales, and stories. It is desirable to name the emotion and its manifestation and explain when and why it can occur.

In some cases, the tasks suggested in class may cause an affective reaction. In such cases, this reaction must not be very strong, as negative impressions of the lesson may cause a refusal to continue the interaction. In addition, it is better than the tasks that can provoke negative emotions to fall on the first part of the lesson, and in the second half, you can do activities that will calm the child and create a positive color. Karvasarskaya (2003) notes that in the case when the child is in a temporary insanity, it is better to slightly increase the duration of the lesson and allow the child to do what gives him/her pleasure so that the end of the lesson was on a positive note.

In addition, in general pedagogy and psychology is known that in order to memorize new material better, especially for children of senior preschool and primary school age, it is recommended to reinforce the

process of assimilation of positive emotions. In addition, emotional uplift is often accompanied by speech manifestations, the desire to express their feelings, which can increase the speech activity of children with autistic disorders.

A child with autistic disorders due to the peculiarities of their development lacks basic trust in the environment, in others. Often negatively emotionally colored personal experience of interaction with the environment further undermines the child's abilities and self-belief. Therefore, in our opinion, the formation of a personal positive experience of communication is especially important.

Thus, the condition of the corrective approach can be determined by the implementation of the correlation of the child's emotional state to form the motivation to learn new speech material and increase speech activity (Bazyma et al., 2020; 2021).

Use of self-stimulation as an integral part of the behavior of a child with autistic disorders

Such pathological conditions of development, as weakness of a tone and sensory-muscular hypersensitivity, cause the creation of individual ways of auto stimulation for each child with autistic disturbances which will increase its mental tone and will reduce constantly arising discomfort, a chronic state of anxiety, and fears and phobias (Khvorova, 2010; Morozova, 2007). The child, again and again, seeks to repeat self-stimulation, thereby limiting the possibility of forming mechanisms of real adaptation to constant changes in the world around and, above all, successful communication with loved ones. A child's particular fascination with sensory experiences can interfere with interaction with the outside world and block an important mechanism of emotional exchange of information with others, limiting the emergence of emotional communication based on speech activity and the desire to communicate through speech. This can be prevented by following the conditions under which self-stimulation occurs, and using them or artificially creating such conditions, during self-stimulation to repeat the child's movements, saying words or phrases (depending on the level of speech of a child with autistic speech disorders) that correspond to the situation. Connection to the child's self-stimulation can be used to establish contact with him/her, increase his/her activity and focus on the world around him/her, organize and complicate ways of interacting with the environment.

Methods of self-stimulation of children with autistic disorders can be

quite diverse and the level of connection to them can also be different. It is important to remember that there are some manifestations of it, the connection to which will be unproductive: trains tied to the experience of strong bodily sensations (in particular, various oral manipulations such as sucking the tongue, cheeks, gnashing teeth, etc.), search special tactile stimuli (causing pain by pressing and pressing on different parts of the body, fixation of certain sensations in the foot, masturbation, etc.); sorting out the texture of objects (stratification of the rope, tearing the paper into small pieces, etc.) (Nikolskaya, 2000; Shulzhenko, 2010). Much more productive is the connection to self-stimulation, which can be like immersion after the child in the flow of his/her enchanting impressions and provide the help he/she needs at the moment - to stretch the detail of the designer, put a piece of the puzzle, mark the movement outside the window, voice, how the car drove, etc. Rhythmic tapping with a toy or an object, spinning the wheel of a car, watching a spinning top, or swinging can be accompanied by sounding and adding emotional content to the activity.

This is a very careful and unhurried work: too many words at once, too short a distance of communication, or a loud voice or a sharp movement can disrupt the emerging moments of joint activities with the child and lead to loss of attention.

Therefore, based on this, the condition of an effective corrective approach can be defined as the use of self-stimulation as an integral part of the child's behavior to fill it with new meaning, which will be the basis for the formation of speech activity.

Using the appropriate number of tasks, the change of which would precede the oversaturation of impressions

Rapid oversaturation with new impressions, on the one hand, and the tendency to defensively reproduce persistent behavioral stereotypes, on the other hand, leads to a reduction in the time to absorb new information. The effectiveness of classes will be much higher if you organize the learning and correction process in such a way that, fed up with one type of activity, the child can immediately change activities, rather than immerse them in the usual stereotypical action. The use of different types of tasks in one lesson will take into account the individual interests of the child, maintain motivation, constantly create a variety of emotional experiences and problem situations, etc. In our opinion, this will help teach children with autistic disorders to transfer previously acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities to new situations, which is an indicator of the development of not only speech but also mental function.

When offering a child a task that may be too difficult, it is recommended to divide it into stages or components, each of which the child can be taught separately. It can master small units at first, but gradually combine them into a more complex system. The point is to start with the elements that she will cope with successfully so that there is an opportunity to encourage the child in some way. This will not only teach the child to perform a task but also lead to increased self-esteem and self-confidence because the child will see the results of his/her activities. A prerequisite is to focus on the child's progress. But, following the principle of optimism, one should not praise the child and exaggerate his/her achievements, because this can lead to a child not understanding whether he/she succeeds. If the task is not completed, despite the efforts of the child, you can break the task into elements or stages to praise the child for the correct execution of a particular element (stage). This, on the one hand, will be the foundation for creating a situation of success and a positive emotional atmosphere, and on the other - will be an impetus to create additional motivation to perform all the elements (stages) of the proposed task. Awareness of the child's success, in our opinion, will help to avoid possible psychological problems associated with speech disorders - reluctance to speak, logophobia (fear of speech).

The TEACCH program offers (Mesibov et al., 2004; Zyumalla, 2005), given the predisposition of children with autism to routine, the tasks prepared for classes should always be placed in the same sequence: most often from left to right: from left there are always unfinished tasks, and from the right - completed. It is recommended to select the number of tasks in such a way that they can be performed in one step. Thus, by the number of uncompleted tasks, the child can understand how much is left to do. When all the tasks are on the right - the lesson ends. According to the daily routine, the child can decide what to do next. This approach can be used for any activity. That is, we are talking about the use in the process of educational and correctional activities of the appropriate number of tasks, the change of which would precede the oversaturation of the impressions of a child with autistic disorders (Bazyra et al., 2020; 2021).

Gradual presentation of tasks with the obligatory use of stimulation as a method of forming motivation for interaction and direct speech activity

Peculiarities of autistic development cause unpredictability in the child's manifestations (mental, behavioral, communicative, emotional, and social). Often, it would seem, simplified exercises and tasks that do not cause

difficulties in children with normal development can be extremely difficult for children with autistic disorders. It is important to find pleasure in small steps forward and rejoice in the achievement of small goals, rather than hoping and fighting for often unattainable and completely inappropriate ideals. Sichkarchuk (2011) and Sheremet (2011) see the development of psychophysiological mechanisms of speech activity in the need to form a motive in the process of organizing speech situations and stimulating emotional speech communication.

According to the concept of creating situations of success by Belkin (1991), the main meaning of the teacher (in our case - a correctional teacher and a special psychologist) is to create a situation of success for each student. Focusing on the research of Shulzhenko (2009), we define the concept of "socio-ecological environment" as a psychological factor in the successful formation of the content component of social and communicative activities of the child, which will be the foundation for the formation of speech activity. Children with autism need to be able see, understand and to be aware of their results. Every step forward, every correctly performed task, every successful attempt should be positively supported and encouraged. In the initial stages of work, encouragement can be quite noticeable and specific like a favorite treat or kiss, but in later work, the encouragement should become more inconspicuous, for example, expressed through a look or other minimal approval of the child's behavior. When verbally encouraging a child with autism, we suggest praising, distinctly, and loudly. These can be the words "Good", "Excellent", "Correct", "Well done", etc. Almost everything a child wants and can get - whether it is food, verbal approval, activity, or a favorite subject - can be used as an incentive, and the more incentives a child has the opportunity to offer, the more effective learning and upbringing will be.

When using incentives and positive incentives to work with children with autistic disorders, it is important to achieve the greatest possible contrast between "negatives" and "positives", especially at the stage of introduction of this technique. If "well done" or "good" sounds the same as "no" or "wrong", then these words have no lexical or emotional content. If the child does not feel a significant difference - it will remain unclear the reason why he receives or does not receive encouragement. That is, the encouragement itself loses its meaning of reinforcing positive behavior (in our case - speech activity).

Getting rid of negatives can also be a form of encouragement. Normally, a child with normal development is concerned about his/her failure and seeks to avoid failure situations. As the number of situation can

be associated with potential failure decrease, the child's anxiety decreases, and the feeling of discomfort disappears.

Lovaas (1987) suggests trying to get the most out of the economic use of incentives. That is, at first, when the child does not yet know or does not fully understand what is required of him, it is recommended to encourage every time the child behaves correctly. Later, as speech activity becomes more frequent and conscious, there is a transition from permanent to partial encouragement, ie the child is encouraged not every time he uses speech, but, for example, only when he initiates speech. This operation of reducing the number of incentives is called "refinement of the schedule of incentives." It is important to note that for each child with autistic disorders, the schedule should be selected individually. If after the "refinement of the schedule of incentives" the child's speech activity decreases, it is necessary to re-introduce more frequent incentives. If the necessary speech activity is fixed - again, you can proceed to reduce the number of incentives.

When using incentives and positive stimulates, it is important to remember that encouragement, whatever it may be, should be immediate. As soon as the child has done the task correctly or done what was required of him, he should receive encouragement within a second. The corrector expected behavior of the child and the reward for it (encouragement) should almost coincide in time. In addition, it is important to move as early as possible and naturally from edible (taste) incentives to social (for example, verbal such as "well done", "good", "right", etc.). If the termination of the child's usual stimuli and the transition to another type of stimuli provokes a decrease in speech activity - it is desirable to return to the use of the type of stimuli that the child perceives best to gradually reduce and replace it later. It is important to gather as much information as possible about the child's habits, interests, and passions before determining the incentive and not to use with all children the methods, techniques, and incentives that have been effective with a particular child.

Thus, the gradual presentation of tasks to children with the obligatory use of stimulation as a method of forming motivation for interaction and direct speech activity is an important condition for the development of speech activity (Bazyma et al., 2020; 2021).

The interaction between specialists and parents of children with autistic disorders

Note that the specialist should not replace parents in attempts to establish interaction with a child with autistic disorders. The mother or the

person replacing the child and the relatives of children with autism should learn to understand all the manifestations of the child, to manage its behavior, to cope with its states of increased anxiety and aggression. And a correctional teacher and a special psychologist should only help in this. To unite the efforts of the specialist and the parents, we recommend that you spend some time discussing the results of the lesson. It is recommended to discuss with the child's mother (or with relatives who spend most of the time with the child) the following points (Yanushko, 2004): the content of the lesson (new knowledge, skills, and abilities that the child gained in class; knowledge, skills, and abilities, which require consolidation at home and in subsequent classes); "incomprehensible" moments (finding out the possible causes of certain verbal or behavioral manifestations - understanding the meaning of words and actions of the child allowed to support his attempt to make contact or communicate and use them in the future to develop new opportunities for communication: as verbal, and nonverbal); the daily life of the child (taking into account the child's regime, family atmosphere, changes in daily routine, interests, passions, and preferences in the construction of classes); new behavioral reactions (statement of moments of progress in the child's development and planning of further corrective actions).

The desire to understand a child with autistic disorders in all the subtleties of its manifestations can be defined as one of the main tasks of correctional work. After all, such an understanding makes it possible not only to explain some features of the child (such as fears, phobias, fantasies, auto stimulations, stereotypes, echolalia, and words and phrases-stamps, etc.) but also to predict possible negative reactions to certain stimuli of the environment, to provoke the necessary reactions for the development of appropriate skills and abilities, to individually select effective games and tasks with educational, educational and corrective content. In addition, passive behavior does not always indicate a lack of interest in other people but may indicate an inability to transform interest into appropriate successful actions (Zyumalla, 2005).

We emphasize the need for the active participation of all family members and relatives in the upbringing of a child with autistic disorders to form various forms of contact.

After all, such a child can come into contact usually in a rigidly stereotypical form, strict adherence to which it often requires from everyone around him/her, and, having the opportunity to communicate with all family members, the child, first, expands the arsenal of forms of interaction, and, secondly, enriches the social-communicative experience. The specialist can help to interpret the child's behavioral and emotional manifestations, suggest

methods and techniques of communication with him/her, and advise on how to organize correctional and developmental classes at home, which will complement the work of correctional educators and special psychologists. Therefore, we focus on the mandatory condition of communication in the work of specialists and parents of children with autistic disorders.

Stimulation of speech activity taking into account the peculiarities of communicative and speech activity of a child with autistic disorders

According to the research of Pakhomova (2006), the improvement of communicative competence requires the formation of the motive of speech activity; development of the initiative in communication; stimulation of non-verbal and verbal means of communication; ability to maintain a conversation on various topics. All these indicators cannot be developed without a sufficient level of speech activity.

According to the results of the experiment (Bazyma et al., 2020; 2021), children with autistic disorders are usually not able to fully communicate, in particular speech communication. Decreased level of speech activity requires stimulation of speech activity taking into account the peculiarities of communicative and speech activity of a child with autistic disorders. For this purpose, methods of forming speech activity were developed:

- creating and maintaining a speech environment;
- constant speech support of the child's activity;
- learning to express opinions in any available way;
- application of incentives and incentives to increase motivation for speech activity;
- use of available vocalizations of the child;
- use of echolalia and tendency to a stereotypical repetition of actions;
- stimulation of speech activity against the background of emotional uplift;
- development of speech activity by imitation;
- activation of passive vocabulary and its gradual transfer to active;
- education of initiative and desire for self-realization.

In addition, it is important to establish and maintain emotional contact with the child, creating a trusting atmosphere of safety and friendliness. Simultaneously with the development of speech activity, the prerequisites for further development of speech are created: the

development of auditory perception, speech breathing, the development of facial and articulatory motility, general and fine motor skills, the accumulation of passive vocabulary, etc. Let's dwell in more detail on the methods of formation of speech activity.

Creating and maintaining a speech environment involves constant maintenance of conversation with the child (even when the child does not respond); the only requirements for speech communication with the child of all adults who most often interact with it; compliance with the speech requirements of the surrounding adults; gradual complication of speech communication; organization of special speech games and exercises.

It is also important to develop an understanding of speech, which occurs both in everyday situations and in the course of specially organized games and exercises. Thus, the work of creating a speech environment for the child is carried out by a speech therapist, educators, psychologist, and parents, because it is important and necessary to use any situation for the development of the child's speech.

Conclusions

A sign of the humanization of the modern pedagogical process is a profound change in its organization, primarily in creating conditions for the formation of a holistic personality of the child. The method of formation of speech activity of children with autistic disorders of senior preschool age can act as an organizational and pedagogical system, which includes the functioning of specific conditions: organizational and pedagogical (the main of which - the creation of educational and corrective and communicative environment); general didactic (continuity, stages, system in the content of the formation of speech activity); technological (pedagogical and speech therapy diagnosis - starting and finishing - of the child as a basis for organizing the formation of speech activity of children with autistic disorders of older preschool age). Among the auxiliary conditions can be distinguished cognitive, creative, and communicative. Taking into account the peculiarities of mental, emotional, communicative, and speech development, we assume that the level of speech activity in children with autistic disorders will increase under the conditions of implementation of our methodology, and providing selected psychological and pedagogical conditions will accelerate and optimize this process.

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